

IN SITU MONITORING OF NANOPARTICLE FILTRATION IN CARBON NANOMATERIAL/GLASS FIBER/ POLYESTER MULTISCALE COMPOSITES DURING VARTM

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1 Introduction

1.1 General Introduction

Fiber reinforced polymeric composites (FRPC_s) are becoming increasingly important in many different industries due mainly to their stiffness to weight ratio and easiness of processability [1, 2]. The need to save energy and to lower the carbon emission is fuelling the increase of composites in aerospace, and in the automotive sectors. The necessity to diversify away from traditional sources of energy is augmenting demand for wind energy, another sector important for composites. Composites are also sought after in sectors dealing with corrosion and construction, as they are strong, resistant to damage and easy to install.

Glass fiber composites are the most popular due to their cheap price and ease of manufacturing, Carbon fiber composites are expensive, but favored in demanding applications such as the aerospace and automotive industries. Strong growth prospects are forecasted as increased energy prices push manufacturers to save costs through using innovative materials. Aramid fiber composites are in demand in security and high-vibration applications, and it is predicted that new uses for aramid fiber will be developed over the forecast period. Other fiber composites and hybrids are forecasted to grow strongly, as sophisticated and purpose-built composites will become necessary for new applications. If Extensive research and development have permitted to reach excellent in-plane properties

of FRPC_s, dominated by microscopic fiber reinforcement, their out-of-plane performance governed by the polymer matrix is very poor and their vulnerability to delamination is of great concern [3]. Differences arise because the polymer matrix presents much lower mechanical properties than the fibers ones, reinforcing the polymer matrix is thus a straightforward solution.

Addition of Carbon based nanofillers, such as carbon nanotubes (CNT_s) and graphene nanoplatelets (GNP_s) or a combination of the two can improve the mechanical, electrical and thermal properties of polymer matrix [4-28]. However an efficient transferability of these nanoreinforcements in a macroscale level of FRPC_s, relies on the capacity to well disperse and distribute them in the host matrix, and also to ensure a good distribution in the fabric.

Nanoreinforcements in their manufactured state tend to cluster together in any suspension due to the strong van der Waals forces at that scale. Shear mixings such as three-roll milling, dissolver disk, planetary mixer and ultrasonic processing or a combination of the two can be used to disperse them in polymer resin to various degree of success [29-36]. Ultrasonication often causes damage on nanofillers resulting in the reduction of their aspect ratio and alters the final nanoreinforced polymer. Three-roll milling has recently provided good results for nanoreinforcement dispersion [37]. It exerts shear forces over the particles and avoids the presence of compression forces during the process, in this way, the agglomerated nanofillers can be

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separated without being damaged provided that the processing parameters such as gap between rolls, rolling speed and numbers of passes are well optimized for the specific type of nanofillers.

When the nanofiller reinforced polymer composite are used to impregnate the fabric in the attempt to replace air/fiber interfaces by resin/fiber interfaces, the final product is called a multiscale composite. This multiscale system shows great promise of incorporating all the subscale advantages into macroscopic properties and will shape the future research in composite area for high-performance multifunctional composites. A typical manufacturing process of these materials is Liquid Composite Moulding (LCM) techniques, the nanofiller reinforced polymer composites is forced to pass through a dry preform placed in a mold. Resin transfer molding and Vacuum assisted resin transfer molding (VARTM) are often used. VARTM is being widely used because it is cost-effective as compared to prepregs technologies which need an autoclave for the curing process.

1.2 General Background

Usually, the fiber preform contains gaps of the order of microns down to 50 nm, one would expect high shear rates to be developed due to the small gaps that may affect the dispersion of the nanoreinforced composites. The flow channels inside the fibrous media can be classified into two categories: An intertow region and an intratow region. The channel width of the intertow region may be up to several hundreds of microns, while that of the intratow region is several microns. The average diameter of a single strand of glass fiber is 17 μ m, while that of the carbon fiber is 7 μ m. When the nanofiller agglomerates are larger than the gaps, woven fabrics always introduce a filtering effect, nanofillers may block these porous gaps leading to a very slow and even insufficient nanocomposites impregnation, this phenomenon is still inevitable mainly around the inlet while the rest of the composite part is lacking nanofillers even for well dispersed suspensions. In the conventional VARTM process, filtration effect always leads to an inhomogeneous [38] microstructure of multiscale composites. So, the final multiscale composite is affected by the initial nanofiller suspension this is the dispersion state and the viscosity and also the porous media structure. In

order to satisfy multifunctional requirements and through-thickness reinforcements without compromising in-plane properties, the processing technique will ineluctably needs to be improved to obtain fully integrated and well dispersed nanofiller. In general, filler size and fibrous pore size dictate the flow of a particle in a fibrous medium, experimentally, as the resin is forced to traverse the porous medium, three cases can be observed: - If the particle size is larger than a critical size that depends on the porous medium characteristics, the particles will accumulate onto the medium and form a cake leading to a cake filtration. - If Particles are very small compared to the pore size, the suspension flows easily in the openness of the medium; there is no or very little retention. - If the suspension flows within the medium, but it progressively captures particles (retention) we will have a deep filtration. In some cases, the amount of retained particles is such that the network is clogged-up. Retention is the case that is most likely to happen in industrial applications. Because of retention and filtration, filler content and, thus, the subsequent property (e.g., fire resistance) are not homogeneous throughout the composite part, which may become defective. In the most severe conditions when the use of high fiber content fabrics or high filler content is necessary, mold filling becomes difficult or hindered.

It is important to effectively investigate the final composite prior to service life. Recognizing the difficulty to experimentally evaluate the filtration phenomenon, many filtration models [39-50] were developed to simulate and predict the particle flow behavior, but these models suffer from precision and are often too much subjective. The few experimental works available rely on tools [21, 51, 52] such as visual flow front distance assessment, composites cross-section observations which require that the composites be destroyed. To meet the demand of high performance multiscale composites, it is important to develop non-destructive experimental method to evaluate the impregnation state in a large scale dimension composite both on the surface and through thickness simultaneously. This will allow to accurately assessing how the manufacturing parameters and processing methods can impart the final multiscale composite and ultimately to meet the needs with high precision.

For CNTs in particular, it has been exceedingly

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difficult to observe filtration phenomena experimentally, because CNTs are made up of carbon atoms, as are the constituents of most polymer resins. Therefore, when CNTs are added as filler particles in the polymer matrix, elemental analysis cannot distinguish between the two components, so S.S. Yum et al [52] recently added silver to CNT and performed quantitative and qualitative analysis to assess particle distribution using electron probe microanalyzer, but this could be possible only for micro-medium in composites. Some researchers have also investigated CNT filtration phenomena in fibrous media using SEM and TEM [21, 51], but these methods only provide qualitative information and do not evaluate the part as a whole.

Herein, as a preliminary work CNT_s (both long and small length) and GNP_s (small and big lateral surface) and the combination of the two were dispersed by a well-defined method using three roll mill in an unsaturated polyester resin (UPE), the mixture were used for infusion by means of conventional and modified VARTM in different porous media.

More importantly and for the first time, in-situ resistance monitoring as a non-destructive method were used to evaluate from infusion to the post-curing process the flow of nanofiller suspension in the porous media. The effects of filler structure and aspect ratio, porous medium, nanofiller suspension dispersion state and manufacturing parameters were investigated. Fabrics such as glass fiber high and low permeability, hybrid woven of carbon and glass fiber were used. As expected, the fillers structure, degree of dispersion, viscosity, fabric permeability, manufacturing parameters dictated the final composites quality. We obtained composites with quasi-homogeneous property which were mechanically and electrically tested and their capacities to structurally self-sense were elucidated. Viscosity as function of temperature was measured and parameters were used to improve the processability of the nanofiller reinforced matrix since the viscosity primarily increases with the dispersion state.

2 Experimental

2.1 Materials

MWCNTs with purity of > 95% and average diameter range of 25-30 nm were purchased from Hanwha Nanotech (Incheon, Korea). The lengths of MWNTs (100 μm and 250 μm) are indicated in their product names, CM-100 and CM-250. Exfoliated graphite nanoplatelets with an average size of 5 μm (xGnP M-5) and 15 μm (xGnP M-15) were purchased from XG Sciences (East Lansing, MI). Plain-woven 3K glass fiber (Mitsubishi) with ply thickness of ~0.2 mm was supplied by JMC (Gyeongju, Korea). DBLT 850-E glass fiber (Cymax) with ply thickness of ~0.6 mm was supplied by Jet Korea (Changwon, Korea). Unsaturated polyester resin, curing agent, and catalyst were supplied by Cray Valley Korea, Arkema, and Jet Korea, respectively. The epoxy resin consisted of three different components. Component A was based on a commercial formula containing bisphenol A YD115J that was provided by Huntsman. Component B was a commercial hardener based on dicyanamide and commercialized as D230, while component C was a commercial latent accelerator based on urones and called A399.

The use of an accelerator allowed for the use of a curing cycle at lower temperatures than those usually required for dicyanamide.

2.2 Nanocomposites fabrication

Nanocomposites were manufactured by following a manufacturing process that consisted of four main steps: first a specific quantity of nanotubes was weighed out to achieve a target weight fractions in the final cured composites (nanotube +epoxy + hardener+ accelerator) and was added to the epoxy resin (YD115J) by hand mixing. Secondly the homogenization and dispersion processes were performed by calendaring, and the parameters used corresponded to the four different calendaring methods (Table 1) being compared in this study. In the third step, the hardener and the accelerator were added to the epoxy resin and stirred manually. The resulting mixture was then degassed using a vacuum machine to aid in the release of the air that had been entrapped in the resin during the calendaring process. The final step involved casting the mixture into an open mold and curing at 60 degrees Celsius for 20 min followed by 80 degree Celsius for 2h. The final nanocomposite dimensions were 80 x10x1mm.

2.3 Multiscale composites fabrication and filtration assessment technology

VARTM is a very attractive, cost effective and environmentally friendly method of processing composites and was used here. The dry fabrics were cut into plies and stacked 2-4 layers to form the dry preform. Four pairs electrodes were placed at the middle of total fabrics in a systematic manner as shown on fig. 1. to track the suspension flow in a real time experiment and sense its behavior with time, doing so the degree at which the fabrics are impregnated this is the degree of nanofiller containing in the suspension is directly related to the resistance level among electrodes measured in-situ during all the fabrication process. This set of paired electrodes can also serve as in situ cure and flow monitoring as well provided that the delay between measurements is sufficiently minimized (< 5 seconds) . The middle of the entirely fabric was chosen to place electrodes because it was the optimal position which provides a good evaluation of the nanofiller distribution. Moreover in attempt to assess flow and cure monitoring, K. V. Uday et al [54] developed a direct current and alternating current sensing/monitoring technique through smart weave, they found that in the case of thin composite panels, wherein the thickness associated gradients are minimal (thickness < 0.125 inch) a single smart weave plane is sufficient. Therefore consolidating the idea that our single plane electrode here is valid because the thicknesses of our final composites are in the range indicated above. The fibrous preform with embedded electrodes are laid on a single-sided plate mold with the capability of the plate mold to be heated (in the case of epoxy), the suspension is then infused through the preform which causes simultaneous wetting in its in-plane and traverse directions. Spiral tubing is utilized for resin suction and infusion lines. Prior to resin injection, vacuum was applied to the mold for 30 min to debulk the preform.

2.4 Characterization of the Materials

For bulk conductivity measurement, CNT reinforced composite were polished to obtain rectangular specimens measuring 80 mm in length and 10 mm in width. Four strips consisting of conductive silver paste were applied to the ends of the specimens to

serve as electrodes. The reason is that CNTs are easily wetted and wrapped by liquid polymers in manufacturing process due to the high surface energy of CNTs, resulting in a high contact resistance between the polymer-wrapped CNTs and a low electrical conductivity of the composites [54, 55]. Electrical resistance (R_v) of the composites was measured by using a digital multimeter (Keithley 2002) for R_v less than $10^7 \Omega$ or using a high-resistance digital meter meter for R_v over $10^7 \Omega$ (Keithley 6517B) alternatively, and the electrical conductivity (σ) of the composites was calculated according to the following formula:

$$\sigma = t / (R_v \times A) \quad (1)$$

where t and A are thickness of the specimens and effective area of the measuring electrodes, respectively.

The surfaces of the composite panels were observed under an optical microscope (MVX10) manufactured by Olympus (Tokyo, Japan), and the microstructure and structural integrity were analyzed. Viscosity measurements were done using a HAAKE MARS III modular rheometer platform from thermo Fisher scientific, Germany. The temperature was controlled electrically using a peltier element (temperature module TM-EL-C), and a cylinder sensor system according to DIN 53019/ISO 3219Z was employed. The sensor system has an extremely small front surface influence and is therefore intended for exact measurement. In order to ensure simultaneous resistance measurements of paired electrodes, Keithley 7001 switching system was used to operate changes from one pair to another.

3 Results and discussions

3.1 Proof-of-concept

To verify our concept, a preliminary experiment was carried out using UPE resin with 0.2wt% of MWNT using method 0 dispersion (Table1). This method is expected to give a very moderate dispersion state with the assurance that nanotubes will preserve their structure and show minimal interaction with UPE chains. Results of the measurement is depicted on fig.2, it is seen that resistances among opposite electrodes placed along the flowing direction (1_8,

2_7, 3_6, and 4_5) decrease from the inlet to the outlet, hence we describe this phenomenon as deep filtration as aforementioned. It is important to observe that resistance 3_6 was placed as an inset of fig 2 because it was so high and could not be overlapped with others but was indeed in our instrument measurement range. For all the resistance values a sudden decrease from infinite to a measured value is observed during resin infusion, and remains averagely constant. For this case we did not observe any significant change of resistance during curing, though it tended to increase due possibly to the effect of cross linking on the viscosity of the thermosetting polymer and the corresponding polymer effect on the mobility of migrating charges which dominates the electrical response upon curing onset. The less CM250 are the higher is the noise or variation on the resistance plot; this could be attributed to a delicate conductive network with particle movements. Fig 2 clearly shows that In-situ resistance monitoring can be used for large dimensions scale investigation and optimization of filtration effect and has the advantage to be non-destructive.

During the three-roll milling process of CM250 reinforced UPE, we have experienced some difficulties. The major concern was the styrene evaporation from the polyester resin during the processes, which caused a dramatic increase of the viscosity. Styrene evaporation was accelerated due to heat occurred on the rolling mills due to higher shear effect. The polyester resin with high viscosity stacked on the rolls and it caused some difficulties for the collection of the resin, due to the uncontrolled styrene evaporation, and thus the final styrene compositions within the resin blends were unknown. This issue was also reported by [22]. To overcome the difficulties associated with styrene evaporation, we switched to a low viscosity epoxy resin of 344.30 cP (20°C) and 45.89 (50°C) as shown on fig.3.

3.1 Nanocomposites dispersion and characterization prior to infusion.

Nanocomposites characterization were carried out to investigate if there is a linear relationship between property transferability in nanocomposites and multiscale composites. For example we want to know if over-dispersion which is detrimental for

nanocomposites by destroying the established network could have an adverse effect in multiscale composites. This may happen due to the decrease of the aspect ratio of nanoparticles, thus easing their passage through fabrics pores sizes. The 3-roll-milling process via intensive shear forces seems to be more convenient technique than traditional ones such as sonication and direct mixing for the dispersion of carbon nanotubes within a liquid polymer resin. Instead of fixing a discrete relation between gap 1 (gap between feed and center roll) and gap 2 (gap between center and apron roll) as A. J. Suarez et al [24] did, we chose gap1 and gap2 that minimize the residence time on nanocomposite by performing several experiments thus optimizing the viscosity of the suspension and promoting good infusion. Method A-C (table1) gave increase viscosity with increasing gap sizes (fig3), it can be seen on fig3 that 0.1% loading does not compromise the infusion.

Moreover optical photo on composites surface (Fig.4.) further evidenced the dispersion state method A-C. Larger agglomerates are still clear in method A, but not visible in method B-C. The surface roughness perceptible in optical photo of method B is rather absent but smooth on method C and could be an indication as well. Furthermore, Method D was revealed as the best conductive samples (Table 1), this can be attributed to optimal dispersion condition. In fact gap 1 was optimized to minimize the residence time and fixed, and gap 2 was fixed to the minimum for the total passes, this could mean that the safety of nanoparticles structure is more related to the gap which collects the fed material than the apron Roll gap, it should not be neither small nor big but just sufficient to disentangle nanoparticles.

A suspension was prepared using method C, and omega lines were used as resin feed and suction lines. We used four DBLT glass fibers instead of two as in the case of UPE presented above, though the filtration phenomenon was still observed but the resistance values substantially decrease (fig.5.); this was attributed to the improvement of dispersion state in the initial suspension.

4 Conclusion

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The proof-of-concept to use a plane of paired electrodes as a tool to evaluate the distribution of nanoparticles in a porous media was demonstrated. The capability of multidimensional functionality of these electrodes was explained. This concept warrants more studies at higher percentages and need to be used to optimize the manufacturing conditions in order to obtain homogeneous multiscale composites.

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Fig.1. Electrode placement scheme at the interface of two DBLT glass fibers.

Fig.2. Resistance changes during infusion and curing in a VARTM process of CM250/UPE.

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Calendering Method	Parameter combination : [gap1 (μm)-gap2 (μm)-speed (rpm)-passes]	Conductivity (S/cm)
Method 0	[60-30-200-6]	
Method A	[60-50-100-2]-[35-20-200-1]	4.57E-06
Method B	[60-50-100-2]-[35-20-200-1]-[20-10-250-3]	2.01E-04
Method C	[60-5-250-2]-[35-5-250-1]-[20-5-250-3]	2.54E-04
Method D	[20-5-250-6]	4.92E-04

Table.1. Calendering dispersion processes employed. The conductivity of neat epoxy is 3.01E-11 S/cm.

Fig.3. Viscosity of CNT/epoxy mixtures at 0.1wt%

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Method A

Method B

Method D

Fig.4. Optical photos surfaces of as-fabricated nanocomposites

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Fig.5. Resistance changes during infusion and curing in a VARTM process of CM250/epoxy at 0.1% loading.